

Potential of methyl fluoride as a universal reaction gas to overcome spectral interference in the determination of ultra-trace concentrations of metals in biofluids using ICP-MS/MS

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Supporting Information

ABSTRACT

Methyl fluoride (a mixture of 10% CH₃F and 90% of He) was evaluated as a reaction gas in ICP-MS/MS in the context of the determination of ultra-trace concentrations of medically relevant metals (Al, Co, Cr, Mn, Ni, Ti and V) in blood serum and urine. Via product ion scanning, whereby only ions of the mass-to-charge ratio of the target nuclide were admitted into the octopole reaction cell, the various reaction product ions formed for each of the target elements were identified at different CH₃F gas flow rates. Limits of detection (LoDs) and of quantification (LoQs) and linearity of the calibration curve were documented under (i) optimized ICP-MS/MS conditions for single-element monitoring and (ii) compromise conditions, allowing for multi-element determination. Even under compromise settings, instrumental LoDs were below 10 ng/L for all target elements, while the use of CH₃F provided interference-free conditions for their determination in the biofluids of interest. Quantitative data obtained for Seronorm blood serum and urine reference materials were in excellent agreement with the corresponding reference values and/or results obtained using double-focusing sector-field ICP-MS (for those elements for which no certified values were available or that were affected during reconstitution), proving the potential of this reaction gas for multi-element ultra-trace analysis via ICP-MS/MS.

INTRODUCTION

The development of suitable multi-element methodologies for the determination of ultra-trace levels in biological samples is still a challenge for analytical chemistry, especially when, as in a biomedical context, high sample throughput without compromised accuracy is required.

An increasing number of light elements (atomic mass ≤ 80 amu) are the target of clinical interest. Aluminium, e.g., has been associated with renal insufficiency and Alzheimer's disease, while its concentration in blood is also promising as a chemical marker for drowning.^{1,2} Titanium is increasingly determined for monitoring patients with metal prostheses. A significant increase in the Ti concentration in biological fluids may indicate prosthesis wear.³⁻⁵ As a result of the various compositions of present-day prostheses and implants, also other elements (e.g., Co, Cr, Mo, Ni and V) need to be determined at ultra-trace levels in this context.⁶⁻⁸ This is an emerging field that requires extremely low limits of detection (LoDs) to properly establish the basal levels, which may be well below $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for some analytes. Also for other purposes, determination of these elements is of biomedical relevance. Vanadium has been suggested for treatment of diabetes, and although it is an essential element, prolonged exposure could cause a variety of health problems.^{9,10} The concentration of Cr is of interest as a result of its role in glucose metabolism and in cardiovascular diseases.^{11,12} Excessive Mn concentrations have proved to result in a neurotoxic accumulation in the brain.^{13,14} Cobalt is a constituent of vitamin B12 and its role in red blood cell production requires the monitoring of this element.^{15,16} Also disproportionate levels of Ni cause disorders or pronounced sensitivity. Many of these Ni-related issues concern the skin, but also breathing problems and even cancer have been mentioned as possible consequences.^{17,18}

Different techniques have been used for ultra-trace element analysis of biofluids, but inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) can be considered as the technique of choice for this purpose, owing to its multi-element capabilities, high detection power and wide linear dynamic range. Nevertheless, even with ICP-MS, the determination of ultra-trace levels of the elements discussed above (mass < 80 amu) in biological fluids is very challenging because of the occurrence of spectral interferences (see Table S1 in the supplementary information SI for a list of potential interferences).^{6,19}

Many of the elements giving rise to interfering species (e.g., C, Ca, Cl, Fe, K, Mg, Na, P and S) are found at much higher levels in biological fluids.

The use of high-resolution sector-field (SF)-ICP-MS is a very elegant way to deal with spectral overlap.¹⁹⁻²² However, an increase in mass resolution is accompanied by a significant drop in ion transmission efficiency and thus, in sensitivity (one to two orders of magnitude). In addition, the cost of the equipment is still considerably higher than that of quadrupole-based (Q)-ICP-MS. Moreover, the use of Q-ICP-MS devices is typically preferred for daily operation in clinical labs owing to their robustness. However, straightforward determination of ultra-trace levels of these elements in difficult matrices has ever been a challenge for Q-ICP-MS, due to the occurrence of spectral interferences.

At the end of the 1990s, multipole collision-reaction cells were introduced in Q-ICP-MS instrumentation, thus improving the selectivity of the technique.²³⁻²⁷ Polyatomic ions can be either slowed down more than atomic ions upon collisions with a non-reactive gas (typically He), such that they can be selectively discriminated against using a decelerating potential²⁸⁻³⁰, or the interfering ion can be removed by selective reaction with the reaction gas. Different gases have been used for the latter purpose, the most frequently used being NH₃, O₂, H₂ and CH₄.³¹⁻³⁵ In most cases, the strategy used consists of removal of the interfering ions, such that the target analyte(s) can be measured interference-free at the original mass/charge ratio.^{36,37} Although often successful, the use of both kinetic energy discrimination and of chemical resolution in a pressurized collision-reaction cell results in a decreased sensitivity for the analyte element(s) as well. With some reactive gases, an alternative approach is also possible, whereby not the interfering ion species but the target ion reacts with gas molecules, thus forming a novel ionic species that can be measured at a different mass/charge ratio. This strategy is successful as long as the interfering ion(s) does not react with the gas molecules, or reacts in a different way.³⁸⁻⁴¹ This approach offers a way to increase selectivity, while preserving sensitivity, if the selected reaction proceeds with high efficiency. However, one of the problems of the first generation of Q-ICP-MS instruments equipped with a collision/reaction cell is that the use of very reactive gases may lead to the production of new interferences. With NH₃, e.g., many protonated clusters of various compositions (e.g., M(NH₂)_x(NH₃)_y⁺) that give rise to signals all across the mass

spectrum are formed.⁴² As a result, very often, the methods proposed were not truly simultaneous, but needed different gases and conditions for different analytes, thus requiring a sequential monitoring. This is a significant drawback when aiming at high sample throughput, when samples are available in small amounts or when monitoring short transient signals (e.g., when using laser ablation, electrothermal vaporization, flow injection analysis or a chromatographic technique for sample introduction).

A new generation of Q-ICP-MS instruments, equipped with what is called a “triple quadrupole” has been introduced in 2013. In this set-up, an additional quadrupole is located before an octopole collision-reaction cell. With this configuration, a tandem mass spectrometer (ICP-MS/MS) is obtained, providing the option of double mass selection. The basic operating principle of such set-up is shown in Figure 1. This type of instrument offers a superior control over the cell chemistry, thus enabling comfortable use of different reaction gases, and enhanced understanding of the reactions proceeding in the cell and the reaction products they give rise to. However, the few papers on ICP-MS/MS published to date have only hinted at this potential, as they have rather focused on mono-element determinations still using “conventional” gases (O_2 and NH_3).^{5,43-48}

In this work, the capabilities of CH_3F as a reaction gas in ICP-MS/MS were evaluated. Some earlier works have investigated the reactions between CH_3F and different elements, but mostly the objective was theoretical (e.g., computational studies or studies that used inductively coupled plasma/selected-ion flow tube (ICP-SIFT) tandem mass spectrometry for studying the mechanism of reaction between CH_3F and selected atomic ions).⁴⁹⁻⁵² Very few papers have actually described the use of methyl fluoride as a reaction gas in Q-ICP-MS,⁵³⁻⁵⁶ probably owing to the complex chemistry. The authors of this work selected CH_3F because it is highly reactive and is involved in different types of reactions with different elements (e.g., fluorination *versus* methyl fluoride addition), both of which are promising features for the purpose of obtaining interference-free conditions for a larger collection of elements.

The main goal of this work was to investigate the potential of ICP-MS/MS to rely on selective chemical reactions with methyl fluoride, with the aim of developing a sensitive and selective method to determine Al, Co, Cr, Mn, Ni, Ti and V in serum and urine samples.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents and standards

Purified water (resistivity > 18.2 M Ω cm) was obtained from a Milli-Q Element water purification system (Millipore, France). Pro analysis purity level 14 M HNO₃ (ChemLab, Belgium) was further purified by sub-boiling distillation. 1 g L⁻¹ single-element standards solutions (Instrument Solutions, The Netherlands) were used for preparing standard solutions (Al, Co, Cr, Mn, Ni, Ti and V) and for matrix-matching (Ca, Cl, Fe, K, Mg, Na, P and S). Throughout the work, external calibration was relied on for calibration, with Ga as an internal standard. All the standards were prepared in 0.14 M HNO₃.

Samples

Two reference materials, SeronormTM Trace Element Serum Level 1 and SeronormTM Trace Element Urine Level 1 (Sero, Norway - Reference 201405 and 210605, respectively) were selected for method development and validation purposes. The selection was carried out based on the clinical relevance of these samples and the presence of most of the target analytes with certified values.

Sample preparation

Because of the low concentrations present in the samples, only metal-free tubes were used for standard solutions and sample preparation (15 or 50 mL polypropylene centrifuge tubes, VWR, Belgium).

Prior to analysis, Seronorm Trace Element Serum and Urine Level 1 were reconstituted in the vials. Following the instructions of the manufacturer, 3 and 5 mL of milli-Q water, respectively, were added to the vials to reconstitute the lyophilized material. To prevent contamination from the vials and the rubber stoppers (especially for Al, as indicated in the product instructions), after 30 minutes the solutions were transferred to Teflon Savillex beakers, which had been thoroughly pre-cleaned (using HNO₃ and HCl and subsequent rinsing with Milli-Q water).

The effect of different dilutions on the extent of signal suppression was evaluated. Taking into account the magnitude of the matrix effect and the concentration of the target analytes, serum and urine samples were diluted 20- and 10-fold with 0.14 M HNO₃, respectively. Gallium was used as an internal standard (final concentration 1 µg L⁻¹). All measurements were performed immediately after the dilution to avoid problems with contamination and sample stability.

Instrumentation

An Agilent 8800 triple-quadrupole ICP-MS instrument (ICP-QQQ, Agilent Technologies, Japan) was used for all measurements. The sample introduction system consisted of a MicroMist nebulizer mounted onto a Peltier-cooled Scott-type spray chamber (2°C). The instrument is equipped with two quadrupole units, one before and one after the octopole reaction cell. The cell can be pressurized with different gases, introduced via one of the four inlets, each having its own mass flow controller. The possibilities of using a mixture of CH₃F and He (10% CH₃F and 90% He) as a reaction gas was tested in this work. The CH₃F/He-mixture was introduced via the 4th inlet, normally used for O₂ (operation range of the mass flow controller: 0 – 100 %, corresponding to gas flow rates of 0 - 1 mL min⁻¹ for O₂).

A Thermo Element XR sector-field ICP-MS instrument (ThermoScientific, Germany) was used for validation purposes, for those target elements for which reference values were not available or in cases of suspected contamination of the samples.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As previously discussed, the determination of some elements at ultra-trace levels in complex matrices is a difficult task for Q-ICP-MS, even when using a collision/reaction cell. ICP-MS/MS allows for a more profound understanding of the chemical resolution of interferences in ICP-MS, as it permits monitoring of all the species formed.^{5,43-48} For that purpose, only ions with an m/z ratio of the target nuclide are allowed to enter the reaction cell by the first quadrupole, while the second quadrupole is scanned as to detect and identify all reaction products formed (product ion scans). Also the possibility

to fix the second quadrupole on a given m/z ratio and to scan the first quadrupole to unravel which ion might be at the origin of a reaction product ion is an interesting tool (precursor ion scan).

In this work, the reactions between CH_3F and Al, Co, Cr, Mn, Ni, Ti and V were studied. All the products formed were evaluated at different gas flow rates. Based on the findings thus obtained, methods were developed for mono-element determination in serum and urine samples under optimum conditions and for multi-element determination under compromise conditions.

Selection of the most suited reaction products at different CH_3F flow rates

The same protocol was applied to all the elements for investigating the different reaction products formed. Solutions containing $5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of Al, Co, Cr, Mn, Ni, Ti or V were prepared and, using the MS/MS capabilities, “product ion scans” were carried out, selecting the exact mass/charge ratio of every target nuclide with the first quadrupole and scanning the entire mass spectrum with the second quadrupole. The study was performed at CH_3F flow rate settings of 0.25, 0.50, 0.75 and 1.00 mL min^{-1} . The results are shown in Figure 2, which presents the signal intensity for the most prominent peaks as a function of the gas flow rate for each element. As an example, a complete product ion scan is provided in the SI (Figure S1). A careful evaluation of these results leads to the following conclusions concerning the identification of the different reaction products ions on the basis of their nominal mass, taking into account the ion-molecule reactions demonstrated in earlier work using ICP-SIFT-MS:⁵¹

- i) Aluminium (^{27}Al , Figure 2a): AlF^+ (m/z 46), AlCH_3F^+ (m/z 61) and AlF_2^+ (m/z 65).
- ii) Titanium (^{48}Ti , Figure 2b): TiF^+ (m/z 67), TiF_2^+ (m/z 86), $\text{TiF}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{F})^+$ (m/z 120), $\text{TiF}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_2^+$ (m/z 154), $\text{TiF}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_3^+$ (m/z 188) and $\text{TiF}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_4^+$ (m/z 222).
- iii) Vanadium (^{51}V , Figure 2c): VF^+ (m/z 70), VF_2^+ (m/z 89), $\text{VF}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{F})^+$ (m/z 123), $\text{VF}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_2^+$ (m/z 157), $\text{VF}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_3^+$ (m/z 191), $\text{VF}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_4^+$ (m/z 225).
- iv) Chromium (^{52}Cr , Figure 2d): CrF^+ (m/z 71), CrCH_3F^+ (m/z 86), $\text{CrF}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})^+$ (m/z 105), $\text{Cr}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_2^+$ (m/z 120), $\text{CrF}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_2^+$ (m/z 139), $\text{CrF}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_3^+$ (m/z 173).
- v) Manganese (^{55}Mn , Figure 2e): MnF^+ (m/z 74), MnCH_3F^+ (m/z 89), $\text{MnF}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})^+$ (m/z 108), $\text{Mn}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_2^+$ (m/z 123), $\text{MnF}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_2^+$ (m/z 142), $\text{MnF}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_3^+$ (m/z 176).

vi) Cobalt (^{59}Co , Figure 2f): CoF^+ (m/z 78), CoCH_3F^+ (m/z 93), $\text{CoF}(\text{CH}_2\text{F})^+$ (m/z 111), $\text{CoF}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})^+$ (m/z 112), $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_2^+$ (m/z 127), $\text{CoF}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_2^+$ (m/z 146), $\text{CoF}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_3^+$ (m/z 180).

vii) Nickel (^{60}Ni , Figure 2g): NiF^+ (m/z 79), NiCH_3F^+ (m/z 94), $\text{NiF}(\text{CH}_2\text{F})^+$ (m/z 112), $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_2^+$ (m/z 128), $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_3^+$ (m/z 162).

Generally speaking, the products formed at lower CH_3F flow rates are the result of fluorine addition (XF_a^+), while increasing the flow rate results in the formation of higher order reaction products, e.g., $\text{XF}_a(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_b^+$ for Cr, Ti and V, and in methyl fluoride addition, e.g., $\text{X}(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_b^+$ for Al, Co, Mn and Ni. It was also possible to group the target elements according to their reactions with CH_3F : (i) Ti and V, (ii) Cr and Mn, and (iii) Co and Ni - for these couples, a very similar behavior with respect to CH_3F was established. Some of our findings (Co, Cr, Mn, Ni, Ti and V) were in agreement with the results of the previously mentioned work carried out by means of ICP-SIFT-MS.⁵¹

To further test the effect of the MS/MS mode on the reactions described above, the same standard solutions were also analyzed in single quadrupole (SQ) mode, thus not prohibiting any ions on the basis of their m/z ratio to enter the octopole reaction cell using the first quadrupole. We observed that under these conditions, the results obtained were different. We hypothesize that this is due to the large amounts of various ubiquitous species that are not removed by the first quadrupole in this case (e.g., N_2^+ , O_2^+ , Ar^+), the presence of which seem to strongly affect the reactions with methyl fluoride.

Although all the products listed above were found, only the products showing a higher intensity were further studied for analytical purposes, as described in the forthcoming sections.

Development of mono-element methods for the determination of each of the analyte elements under optimum conditions

For mono-element determination of the target nuclides, the reaction product ions characterized by the highest intensity were selected. The mass of the target analyte and the mass of the corresponding reaction product ion were fixed via the first and second quadrupole, respectively. The optimum gas flow rate was selected to maximize the signal/background ratio (Intensity for $5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in 0.14 M

HNO₃). Under these optimum conditions, for every target analyte, 10 consecutive measurements of 5 standard solutions (concentrations of 0, 0.5, 1, 2.5 and 5 µg L⁻¹) were carried out. Table 1 shows the different products that were finally used for quantification purposes with the corresponding methyl fluoride flow rate settings, as well as the calibration data and the instrumental limits of detection and quantification (LoDs and LoQs were calculated as $3S_{\text{blank}}/\text{slope}$ and $10S_{\text{blank}}/\text{slope}$, respectively). As can be seen, the LoDs for all of the elements and nuclides are, at least for one of the reaction product ions, below 10 ng L⁻¹. It has to be stressed that these are the instrumental LoDs, such that sample dilution needs to be considered to obtain the final LoD in real-life analysis. Comparison with figures of merit obtained via other types of ICP-MS may serve to evaluate the potential of ICP-MS/MS for the determination of ultra-trace levels of these elements (Table 2).

Although it is always difficult to compare LoDs that have been obtained under different circumstances, the LoDs found with ICP-MS/MS are superior to those obtained with Q-ICP-MS (equipped with collision/reaction cell) in all cases, and are in good agreement with those obtained via SF-ICP-MS. Special attention can be paid to the case of Ti (LoDs with CH₃F, 0.9 – 3 ng L⁻¹), as it is possible to carry out a direct comparison with a previous work, based on ICP-MS/MS⁵ with NH₃ as reaction gas. A 3-fold improvement (LoDs with NH₃, 3 – 10 ng L⁻¹) was found, further proving the benefits of using CH₃F.

It can be concluded that, even though sample dilution needs to be taken into account, the LODs achieved in this work are certainly fit for the purpose of analysis of biological fluids.

As most of the elements under investigation are severely affected by spectral overlap in clinical matrices, it is also important to investigate the capabilities of the methods developed to avoid these interferences. Therefore, matrix-matched standard solutions were prepared by adding 10 mg L⁻¹ of the most important matrix elements present in clinical samples (Ca, Cl, Fe, K, Mg, Na, P, and S) to 5 µg L⁻¹ of the analyte elements. Only in the case of Ti, the results obtained were affected by the presence of the interfering species (formation of ^{46,48}CaF⁺ and ⁴⁸CaF₂(CH₃F)₃⁺, overlapping with ^{46,48}TiF⁺ and, to a lesser extent, with ⁴⁸TiF₂(CH₃F)₃⁺, respectively). Due to the importance of this interference, especially in the case of ^{46,48}TiF⁺, and to the presence of high Ca concentrations in

clinical samples, these two species were not further investigated. However, the monitoring of other reaction product ions ($^{47,49,50}\text{TiF}^+$ and $^{46,47,49,50}\text{TiF}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_3^+$) should allow interference-free Ti determination.

Mono-element determinations of ultra-trace elements in Seronorm Trace Elements Serum and Urine Level 1

Once all the mono-element methods were developed, two different reference materials were analyzed for validation purposes: Seronorm Trace Element Serum Level 1 and Seronorm Trace Element Urine Level 1.

Several sub-samples from one vial were analyzed with ICP-MS/MS and the results were compared with the certified values. For those target elements for which the concentrations are not certified and only indicative values (or even no reference values at all) are available, SF-ICP-MS was used for validation purposes (see SI Table S2). The results thus obtained are shown in Table 3.

A good agreement between ICP-MS/MS results and the reference values was found in all cases ($t < t_{\text{critical}}$ at a 95% level of significance), with uncertainty intervals overlapping, except for Al. For this element, the value obtained by means of ICP-MS/MS was biased high (particularly for urine). However, the value obtained is in good agreement with the result obtained by means of SF-ICP-MS ($t < t_c$), thus revealing possible contamination problems during the reconstitution of the samples, which is a common issue, also indicated in the certificate of the materials. For those analytes for which indicative values are provided – Ti in serum and urine and V in serum – or for which no reference value at all is available – Cr in urine – the results were compared with those obtained via SF-ICP-MS. No significant differences were found for V and Cr ($t < t_{\text{critical}}$ for all reaction products and nuclides), nor for Ti for the reaction product ions $^{47,49}\text{TiF}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{F})_3^+$. However, significant differences were found when considering the results obtained using the reaction product ions $^{47,49,50}\text{TiF}^+$. Unfortunately, and although a precursor ion scan was used in an attempt to identify the interferences which produce inaccuracy in the results, the species responsible were not found. In any case, the results show that an interference-free determination of at least two isotopes is possible for Cr, Ni and Ti, thus opening a way for isotopic analysis, e.g., in the context of elemental assay *via* isotope dilution or in tracer

experiments with stable isotopes. This aspect is particularly remarkable for ^{58}Ni , because of the isobaric interference with ^{58}Fe and the high concentration of iron present in serum (1.39 mg L^{-1}). This indicates that, under the experimental conditions used in this work, Ni and Fe ions react differently with CH_3F or that, due to the low abundance of ^{58}Fe , the final result was not affected.

Development of a multi-element method for the simultaneous determination of Al, Co, Cr, Mn, Ni, Ti and V

As described before, the optimum instrument settings providing the highest signal intensity are different for each element, because of the influence of the CH_3F flow rate on the reactions taking place in the reaction cell. However, the development of a multi-element method, allowing for an accurate and simultaneous determination of all of the elements of interest would be of much higher value for routine analysis. Therefore, based on the results presented in Figure 2, it was investigated whether such compromise conditions could be found. Due to the significant reduction of sensitivity found at lower CH_3F flow rates, particularly for Co, Mn and Ni, the maximum flow rate setting (1 mL min^{-1}) was selected. Once the CH_3F flow rate was chosen, the other parameters were also optimized (see SI Table S2). Calibration data and LoDs and LoQs obtained via measurement of 5 multi-element standard solutions (concentration range between 0 to $5 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) are shown in Table 4. Although under these conditions, a 20-30% reduction in signal intensity was observed for Al, Ti and V, the LoDs were not affected significantly and again, they were found to be below 10 ng L^{-1} in all cases.

Simultaneous multi-elemental analysis of Seronorm Trace Elements Serum and Urine Level 1

The samples analyzed via the mono-element methods were also analyzed using the multi-element method, enabling a direct comparison of the results (Table 3). At a 95% level of confidence, no significant differences were found between the results obtained under optimum conditions for every analyte and those obtained under multi-element compromise conditions ($t < t_{\text{critical}}$), except for ^{46}Ti in urine, where the difference was found to be statistically significant, although the t value is close to t_{critical} ($2.77 > 2.31$). Also in terms of precision, no significant differences could be established at a 95% level of confidence (F-test: $F < F_{\text{critical}}$). RSD values range between 1 – 6 %, which is fit for purpose for

the application intended, except for Cr in urine for which the RSD was higher, especially for the less abundant isotope ^{53}Cr (5 – 18 %).

To check the reproducibility of the method for different samples (different vials with reference material from the same batch), the same samples discussed previously and four additional samples (two vials for serum and two vials for urine) were analyzed using the multi-element method. The results are shown in the SI (Table S3), showing the average concentration and the standard deviation for three different samples (vials) from the same batch – each sample was analyzed 10 consecutive times. ANOVA indicated that there is significant variation between the results for the different samples, except for $^{47,49,50}\text{Ti}$ and ^{59}Co in serum, and ^{53}Cr and ^{60}Ni in urine ($F < F_{\text{critical}}$). These variations are particularly important in the case of Al for both serum and urine ($F_{\text{Al,serum}} = 192.31$; $F_{\text{Al,urine}} = 278.84 > F_{\text{critical}} = 3.35$) and of Ti in urine ($F_{\text{Ti (46-50)}} = 39.24 - 108.75 > F_{\text{critical}} = 3.35$). These results suggest that, at these concentration levels, issues like sample preparation, sample storage and contamination, become more challenging than the analysis using ICP-MS/MS itself.

CONCLUSION

In this work, the utility of ICP-MS/MS with methyl fluoride (a mixture of 10% CH_3F and 90 % He) as a reaction gas was demonstrated for the determination of ultra-trace levels of Al, Co, Cr, Mn, Ni, Ti and V in serum and urine samples.

In a first phase, for each target element, product ion scans have been performed at different CH_3F flow rates. Based on these results, optimized mono-element methods have been developed, allowing full exploitation of the possibilities of ICP-MS/MS for each analyte. In all cases, excellent detection limits (below 10 ng L^{-1}) could be obtained. Additionally, it was also demonstrated that a multi-element method for the simultaneous determination of all the target elements under a same set of instrument settings did not compromise the accuracy and precision of the results. Interference-free conditions were obtained for all elements studied. It has also been found that for elements such as Cr, Ni and Ti, at least two isotopes could be measured interference-free, enabling isotopic analysis.

Overall, the satisfactory results obtained suggest that the use of CH₃F is a valuable alternative for the more common reaction gases used nowadays. Finally, it has been shown that ICP-MS/MS does not only allow interference-free determination of traditionally interfered elements, but is also a versatile tool to systematically study the complex reactions taking place in a reaction cell in a very straightforward way.

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ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Additional information is indicated in the text. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

References

- (1) Sariego Muñiz, C.; Marchante-Gayón, J. M.; García Alonso J. I.; Sanz-Medel, A. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **1998**, 13, 283 – 287.
- (2) Aramendía, M.; Flórez, M. R.; Piette, M.; Vanhaecke, F.; Resano, M. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2011**, 26, 1964 – 1973.
- (3) Richardson, T. D.; Pineda, S. J.; Strenge, K. B.; Van Fleet, T. A.; MacGregor, M.; Milbrandt, J. C.; Espinosa, J. A.; Freitag, P. *Spine* **2008** 33, 792 – 796.
- (4) Rello, L; Lapeña, A. C.; Aramendía, M.; Belarra, M. A.; Resano, M. *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B* **2013**, 81, 11 – 19.
- (5) Balcaen, L.; Bolea-Fernandez, E.; Resano, M.; Vanhaecke, F. *Anal. Chim. Acta* **2014**, 809, 1 – 8.
- (6) Sarmiento-González, A.; Marchante-Gayón, J. M.; Tejerina-Lobo, J. M.; Paz-Jiménez, J.; Sanz-Medel, A. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* **2005**, 382, 1001 – 1009.
- (7) Sarmiento-González, A.; Marchante-Gayón, J. M.; Tejerina-Lobo, J. M.; Paz-Jiménez, J.; Sanz-Medel, A. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* **2008**, 391, 2583 – 2589.
- (8) Engh Jr. C. A.; MacDonald, S. J.; Sritulanondha, S.; Thompson, A.; Naudie, D.; Engh, C.A. *Clin. Orthop. Relat. Res.* **2009**, 467, 101 – 111.
- (9) Willsky, G. R.; Goldfine, A. B.; Kostyniak, P. J.; McNeill, J. H.; Yang, L. Q.; Khan, H. R.; Crans, D. C. *J. Inorg. Biochem.* **2001**, 85, 33 – 42.
- (10) Yang, L.; Sturgeon, R. E.; Prince, D.; Gabos, S. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2002**, 17, 1300 – 1303.
- (11) Bonnefoy, C.; Menudier, A.; Moesch, C.; Lachâtre, G. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* **2005**, 383, 167 – 173.
- (12) Cieslak, W.; Pap, K.; Bunch, D. R.; Reineks, E.; Jackson, R.; Steinle, R.; Wang, S. *Clin. Biochem.* **2013**, 46, 266 – 270.
- (13) Aschner, M.; Guilarte, T. R.; Schneider, J. S.; Zheng, W. *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* **2007**, 221, 131 – 147.
- (14) Michalke, B.; Lucio, M.; Berthele, A.; Kanawati, B. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* **2013**, 405, 2301 – 2309.

- (15) Schwingel Ribeiro, A.; Antunes Vieira, M.; Furtado da Silva, A.; Gallindo Borges, D. L.; Welz, B.; Heitmann, U.; Curtius, A. J. *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B* **2005**, 60, 693 – 698.
- (16) Gornet, M. F.; Burkus, J. K.; Harper, M. L.; Chan, F. W.; Skipor, A. K.; Jacobs, J. J. *Eur. Spine J.* **2013**, 22, 741 – 746.
- (17) Xu, S. X.; Stuhne-Sekatec, L.; Templeton, D. M. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **1993**, 8, 445 – 448.
- (18) Ferreira, S. L. C.; dos Santos, W. N. L.; Lemos, V. A. *Anal. Chim. Acta* **2001**, 445, 145 – 151.
- (19) Schramel, P.; Wendler, I. *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.* **1998**, 361, 487 – 491.
- (20) Riondato, J.; Vanhaecke, F.; Moens, L.; Dams, R. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **1997**, 12, 933 – 937.
- (21) Jakubowski, N.; Moens, L.; Vanhaecke, F. *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B* **1998**, 53, 1739 – 1763.
- (22) Krachler, M.; Heisel, C.; Kretzer, J. P. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2009**, 24, 605 – 610.
- (23) Tanner, S. D.; Baranov, V. I. *At. Spectrosc.* **1999**, 20 (2), 45 – 52.
- (24) Baranov, V. I.; Tanner, S. D. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **1999**, 14, 1133 – 1142.
- (25) Tanner, S. D.; Baranov, V. I. *J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom.* **1999**, 10, 1083 – 1094.
- (26) Tanner, S. D.; Baranov, V. I.; Vollkopf, U. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2000**, 15, 1261 – 1269.
- (27) Tanner, S. D.; Baranov, V. I.; Bandura, D. R. *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B* **2002**, 57, 1361 – 1452.
- (28) Feldmann, I.; Jakubowski, N.; Stuewer, D. *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.* **1999**, 365, 415 – 421.
- (29) Feldmann, I.; Jakubowski, N.; Stuewer, D. *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.* **1999**, 365, 422 – 428.
- (30) Boulyga, S. F.; Becker, J. S. *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.* **2001**, 370, 618 – 623.
- (31) Bandura, D. R.; Baranov, V. I.; Tanner, S. D. *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.* **2001**, 370, 454 – 470.
- (32) Hattendorf, B.; Günther, D. *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B* **2003**, 58, 1 – 13.
- (33) Koppelaar, D. W.; Eiden, G. C.; Barinaga, C. J. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2004**, 19, 561 – 570.
- (34) Olesik, J. W.; Jones, D. R. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2006**, 21, 141 – 159.
- (35) Grotti, M.; Soggia, F.; Todoli, J. L. *Analyst* **2008**, 133, 1388 – 1394.
- (36) Simpson, L. A.; Thomsen, M.; Alloway, B. J.; Parker, A. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2001**, 16, 1375 – 1380.
- (37) Resano, M.; Garcia-Ruiz, E.; Vanhaecke, F. *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B* **2005**, 60, 1472 – 1481.
- (38) Bandura, D. R.; Baranov, V. I.; Tanner, S. D. *Anal. Chem.* **2002**, 74, 1497 – 1502.
- (39) Bandura, D. R.; Ornatsky, O. I.; Liao, L. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2004**, 19, 96 – 100.

- (40) Yang, C. H.; Jiang, S. J. *Spectrochim. Acta, Part B* **2004**, 59, 1389 – 1394.
- (41) Bandura, D. R.; Baranov, V.; Litherland, A. E.; Tanner, S. D. *Int. J. Mass Spectrom.* **2006**, 255-256, 312 – 327.
- (42) Hattendorf, B.; Günther, D. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2000**, 15, 1125 – 1131.
- (43) Diez Fernández, S.; Sugishama, N.; Ruiz Encinar, J.; Sanz-Medel, A. *Anal. Chem.* **2012**, 84, 5851 – 5857.
- (44) Balcaen, L.; Woods, G.; Resano, M.; Vanhaecke, F. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2013**, 28, 33 – 39.
- (45) Ohno, T.; Muramatsu, Y.; Shikamori, Y.; Toyama, C.; Okabe, N.; Matsuzaki, H. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2013**, 28, 1283 – 1287.
- (46) Tanimizu, M.; Sugiyama, N.; Ponzevera, E.; Bayon, G. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2013**, 28, 1372 – 1376.
- (47) Ohno, T.; Muramatsu, Y. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2014**, 29, 347 – 351.
- (48) Böting, K.; Treu, S.; Leonhard, P.; Heiß, C.; Bings, N. H. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2014**, 29, 578 – 582.
- (49) Mazurek, U.; Schwarz, H. *Chem. Commun.* **2003**, 1321 – 1326.
- (50) Koyanagi, G. K.; Zhao, X.; Blagojevic, V.; Jarvis, M. J. Y.; Bohme, D. K. *Int. J. Mass Spectrom.* **2005**, 241, 189 – 196.
- (51) Zhao, X.; Koyanagi, G. K.; Bohme, D. K. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2006**, 110, 10607 – 10618.
- (52) Redondo, P.; Varela-Álvarez, A.; Rayón, V. M.; Largo, A.; Sordo, J. A.; Barrientos, C. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2013**, 117, 2932 – 2943.
- (53) Moens, L. J.; Vanhaecke, F.; Bandura, D. R.; Baranov, V. I.; Tanner, S. D. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2001**, 16, 991 – 994.
- (54) Vanhaecke, F.; Balcaen, L.; Deconinck, I.; De Schrijver, I.; Almeida, C. M.; Moens, L. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2003**, 18, 1060 – 1065.
- (55) Nonose, N.; Ohata, M.; Narukawa, T.; Hioki, A.; Chiba, K. *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* **2009**, 24, 310 – 319.
- (56) D’Ilio, S.; Violante, N.; Majorani, C.; Petrucci, F. *Anal. Chim. Acta* **2011**, 698, 6 – 13.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of ICP-MS/MS operation using $\text{CH}_3\text{F}/\text{He}$ as reaction gas (m/z represents the mass/charge ratio of the corresponding analytes (A), interferences (I) and/or reaction product ions).

Figure 2. Selection of the different species formed at different methyl fluoride flow rate settings. The species ultimately used to determine the different target analytes are marked in red.

Table 1. Calibration data and instrumental limits of detection (LoD) and of quantification (LoQ) obtained for monoelemental methods in optimal conditions with ICP-MS/MS

Isotope	CH ₃ F/He flow rate (mL min ⁻¹)	Reaction product ion	Q1 (amu)	Q2 (amu)	Sensitivity ^a (L.µg ⁻¹)	Intercept ^a (counts.s ⁻¹)	R ²	LoD ^b (µg.L ⁻¹)	LoQ ^b (µg.L ⁻¹)
²⁷ Al	0.25	²⁷ AlF ⁺	27	46	3489 ± 21	686 ± 63	0.9997	0.01	0.04
	1.00	²⁷ AlCH ₃ F ⁺		61	8021 ± 93	1401 ± 130	0.9997	0.008	0.03
⁴⁶ Ti	0.40	⁴⁶ TiF ⁺	46	65	1412 ± 32	98 ± 37	0.9998	0.02	0.07
	0.90	⁴⁶ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺		186	1723 ± 19	34 ± 23	0.99996	0.003	0.01
⁴⁷ Ti	0.40	⁴⁷ TiF ⁺	47	66	1425 ± 26	59 ± 21	0.9998	0.003	0.009
	0.90	⁴⁷ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺		187	1673 ± 19	39 ± 25	0.9998	0.003	0.009
⁴⁸ Ti	0.40	⁴⁸ TiF ⁺	48	67	15880 ± 210	2980 ± 200	0.9994	0.02	0.07
	0.90	⁴⁸ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺		188	17920 ± 180	250 ± 200	0.99998	0.0009	0.003
⁴⁹ Ti	0.40	⁴⁹ TiF ⁺	49	68	1286 ± 27	46 ± 34	0.9998	0.03	0.09
	0.90	⁴⁹ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺		189	1445 ± 20	27 ± 27	0.99998	0.003	0.01
⁵⁰ Ti	0.40	⁵⁰ TiF	50	69	1429 ± 25	71 ± 34	0.9997	0.007	0.02
	0.90	⁵⁰ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺		190	1455 ± 12	29 ± 15	0.99995	0.002	0.006
⁵¹ V	0.40	⁵¹ VF ⁺	51	70	39250 ± 740	420 ± 470	0.99997	0.0009	0.003
	0.80	⁵¹ VF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺		191	40160 ± 330	230 ± 140	0.999997	0.0001	0.0004
⁵² Cr	0.45	⁵² CrF ⁺	52	71	12940 ± 110	61 ± 51	0.9999995	0.002	0.005
	1.00	⁵² Cr(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺		120	8027 ± 41	62 ± 33	0.99998	0.0009	0.003
	1.00	⁵² CrF(CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺		173	7628 ± 55	-25 ± 43	0.999992	0.003	0.01
⁵³ Cr	0.45	⁵³ CrF ⁺	53	72	1495 ± 23	17 ± 17	0.99998	0.004	0.01
	1.00	⁵³ Cr(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺		121	994 ± 18	11 ± 15	0.99994	0.006	0.02
	1.00	⁵³ CrF(CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺		174	907 ± 12	-2 ± 10	0.999994	0.01	0.03
⁵⁵ Mn	1.00	⁵⁵ Mn(CH ₃ F) ⁺	55	89	11846 ± 76	47 ± 71	0.9999997	0.001	0.004
⁵⁹ Co	1.00	⁵⁹ Co(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	59	127	46230 ± 410	320 ± 370	0.999992	0.0003	0.0009
⁵⁸ Ni	1.00	⁵⁸ Ni(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	58	126	14829 ± 67	85 ± 52	0.999997	0.002	0.008
⁶⁰ Ni	1.00	⁶⁰ Ni(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	60	128	6280 ± 42	35 ± 42	0.99998	0.002	0.007

^a Uncertainties expressed as standard deviation (n = 10)

^b LoDs and LoQs calculated as 3 and 10 times the standard deviation on 10 consecutive measurements of a blank solution (0.14 M HNO₃), divided by the slope of the calibration curve, respectively.

Table 2. Comparison between the LoDs found via ICP-MS/MS and those reported in the literature based on the use of other types of ICP-MS devices (ng L^{-1}).^{1,6,7,14}

Isotopes	Q-ICP-MS ^a	SF-ICP-MS	ICP-MS/MS
²⁷ Al	130	50	8
⁴⁷ Ti	70	10	3
⁵¹ V	3	0.1	0.1
⁵² Cr	6	0.1	0.9
⁵⁵ Mn	20	10	1
⁵⁹ Co	7	0.1	0.3
⁶⁰ Ni	30	5	2

^aValues obtained from different papers; the gases most often used in collision-reaction cells were He, H₂, NH₃.

Table 3. Results obtained for Seronorm Trace Element Serum L-1 and Seronorm Trace Element Urine L-1 same vial

		Seronorm Trace Elements Serum L-1					Seronorm Trace Elements Urine L-1				
Analyte	Reaction product ion	Mono-element ICP-MS/MS ^a (µg L ⁻¹)	Multi-element ICP-MS/MS ^a (µg L ⁻¹)	SF-ICP-MS ^b (µg L ⁻¹)	Reference value (µg L ⁻¹)	Acceptable range (µg L ⁻¹)	Monoelemental ICP-MS/MS ^a (µg L ⁻¹)	Multielemental ICP-MS/MS ^a (µg L ⁻¹)	SF-ICP-MS ^b (µg L ⁻¹)	Reference value (µg L ⁻¹)	Acceptable range (µg L ⁻¹)
²⁷ Al	²⁷ AlF ⁺	40.55 ± 0.84	—	—	—	—	14.31 ± 0.20	—	—	—	—
	²⁷ AlCH ₃ F ⁺	40.29 ± 0.73	40.00 ± 0.55	40.73 ± 0.83	33.6 ± 1.9	29.8 – 37.4	14.38 ± 0.33	13.88 ± 0.55	14.62 ± 0.22	4.6 ± 3.5	1.1 – 8.1
⁴⁶ Ti	⁴⁶ TiF ⁺	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	⁴⁶ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	12.28 ± 0.64	12.68 ± 0.71	—	—	11.2 ^c	13.31 ± 0.37	12.68 ± 0.35	—	—	13.5 ^c
⁴⁷ Ti	⁴⁷ TiF ⁺	14.71 ± 0.69	—	—	—	11.2 ^c	26.06 ± 0.86	—	—	—	—
	⁴⁷ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	11.88 ± 0.38	11.83 ± 0.49	11.58 ± 0.53	—	11.2 ^c	12.87 ± 0.50	12.38 ± 0.49	12.76 ± 0.20	—	13.5 ^c
⁴⁸ Ti	⁴⁸ TiF ⁺	—	—	—	—	11.2 ^c	—	—	—	—	—
	⁴⁸ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	14.10 ± 0.35	—	—	—	11.2 ^c	14.60 ± 0.17	—	—	—	13.5 ^c
⁴⁹ Ti	⁴⁹ TiF ⁺	17.46 ± 0.59	—	—	—	11.2 ^c	14.88 ± 0.47	—	—	—	—
	⁴⁹ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	11.44 ± 0.56	11.90 ± 0.48	11.81 ± 0.33	—	11.2 ^c	12.82 ± 0.30	12.62 ± 0.57	12.72 ± 0.21	—	13.5 ^c
⁵⁰ Ti	⁵⁰ TiF	37.42 ± 1.79	—	—	—	11.2 ^c	24.36 ± 0.72	—	—	—	—
	⁵⁰ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	11.29 ± 0.51	11.83 ± 0.55	—	—	11.2 ^c	12.77 ± 0.40	12.42 ± 0.31	—	—	13.5 ^c
⁵¹ V	⁵¹ VF ⁺	1.20 ± 0.05	—	—	—	0.96 ^c	0.70 ± 0.03	—	—	—	—
	⁵¹ VF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	1.23 ± 0.01	1.23 ± 0.03	1.19 ± 0.03	—	0.96 ^c	0.73 ± 0.02	0.77 ± 0.04	0.74 ± 0.01	0.66 ± 0.08	0.5 – 0.9
⁵² Cr	⁵² CrF ⁺	1.42 ± 0.04	—	—	—	—	1.51 ± 0.12	—	—	—	—
	⁵² Cr(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	1.45 ± 0.04	1.46 ± 0.08	1.46 ± 0.06	1.5 ± 0.2	1.1 – 1.9	1.66 ± 0.18	1.61 ± 0.27	1.65 ± 0.27	—	—
	⁵² CrF(CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	1.41 ± 0.03	—	—	—	—	1.52 ± 0.26	—	—	—	—
⁵³ Cr	⁵³ CrF ⁺	1.37 ± 0.07	—	—	—	—	1.57 ± 0.18	—	—	—	—
	⁵³ Cr(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	1.43 ± 0.06	1.43 ± 0.10	1.41 ± 0.10	1.5 ± 0.2	1.1 – 1.9	1.64 ± 0.20	1.63 ± 0.29	1.63 ± 0.05	—	—
	⁵³ CrF(CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	1.46 ± 0.10	—	—	—	—	1.66 ± 0.18	—	—	—	—
⁵⁵ Mn	⁵⁵ Mn(CH ₃ F) ⁺	15.14 ± 0.07	15.25 ± 0.13	—	15.0 ± 0.9	13.2 – 16.8	0.68 ± 0.02	0.69 ± 0.05	—	0.73 ± 0.15	0.44 – 1.02
⁵⁹ Co	⁵⁹ Co(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	1.19 ± 0.03	1.22 ± 0.05	—	1.2 ± 0.2	0.9 – 1.5	0.71 ± 0.01	0.72 ± 0.01	—	0.72 ± 0.15	0.43 – 1.01
⁵⁸ Ni	⁵⁸ Ni(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	5.64 ± 0.14	5.58 ± 0.08	—	5.8 ± 0.7	4.5 – 7.1	1.55 ± 0.03	1.56 ± 0.06	—	1.51 ± 0.30	0.91 – 2.11
⁶⁰ Ni	⁶⁰ Ni(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	5.63 ± 0.13	5.58 ± 0.20	—	5.8 ± 0.7	4.5 – 7.1	1.57 ± 0.07	1.58 ± 0.11	—	1.51 ± 0.30	0.91 – 2.11

^a Uncertainties expressed as standard deviation (n = 5)

^b Uncertainties expressed as standard deviation (n = 3)

^c Indicative value

Table 4. Calibration data and instrumental limits of detection (LoD) and quantification (LoQ) obtained for the ICP-MS/MS multi-element method

Isotope	Reaction product ion	Q1 (amu)	Q2 (amu)	Sensitivity ^a (L.μg ⁻¹)	Intercept ^a (counts.s ⁻¹)	R ²	LoD ^b (μg.L ⁻¹)	LoQ ^b (μg.L ⁻¹)
²⁷ Al	²⁷ AlCH ₃ F ⁺	27	61	6233 ± 57	1069 ± 46	0.9990	0.01	0.03
⁴⁶ Ti	⁴⁶ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	46	186	1346 ± 16	43 ± 16	0.99995	0.003	0.01
⁴⁷ Ti	⁴⁷ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	47	187	1315 ± 16	52 ± 31	0.99990	0.001	0.004
⁴⁹ Ti	⁴⁹ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	49	189	1026 ± 35	40 ± 29	0.99998	0.002	0.008
⁵⁰ Ti	⁵⁰ TiF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	50	190	1101 ± 18	32 ± 33	0.99993	0.003	0.01
⁵¹ V	⁵¹ VF ₂ (CH ₃ F) ₃ ⁺	51	191	29780 ± 220	-410 ± 220	0.99996	0.0002	0.0008
⁵² Cr	⁵² Cr(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	52	120	7298 ± 79	137 ± 63	0.99998	0.004	0.01
⁵³ Cr	⁵³ Cr(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	53	121	910 ± 27	8 ± 27	0.9999995	0.01	0.03
⁵⁵ Mn	⁵⁵ Mn(CH ₃ F) ⁺	55	89	11320 ± 110	247 ± 69	0.99997	0.001	0.005
⁵⁹ Co	⁵⁹ Co(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	59	127	50050 ± 110	720 ± 160	0.99998	0.0006	0.002
⁵⁸ Ni	⁵⁸ Ni(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	58	126	15180 ± 100	190 ± 130	0.999995	0.002	0.005
⁶⁰ Ni	⁶⁰ Ni(CH ₃ F) ₂ ⁺	60	128	5850 ± 41	94 ± 67	0.99998	0.003	0.009

^a Uncertainties expressed as standard deviation (n=10)

^b LoDs and LoQs calculated as 3 and 10 times the standard deviation on 10 consecutive measurements of a blank solution (0.14M HNO₃), divided by the slope of the calibration curve, respectively.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ICP-MS/MS

